

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SARKADY****FIRST NAME: EMESE****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on macOS Sonoma)

List your 5 key concepts with page number in text

1. Starting, researching an essay and organizing thoughts (EUCLID 2024, 7-9)
2. Punctuation (EUCLID 2024, 16-23)
3. American versus British English (EUCLID 2024, 25-26)
4. Plagiarism and style guide (EUCLID 2024, 34-57)
5. Latin abbreviations (EUCLID 2024, 59.64)

WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

Writing an essay is a complex task. It requires not only knowledge of the chosen topic but also constructive, didactical thinking and a good command of the language in which the essay is written, including grammar, spelling, and punctuation. However, writing an academic essay requires an even more stringent application of rules, which includes thorough research, exact use of style, referencing, and editing. EUCLID University has a particular way of writing academic essays, the rules of which are summarized in the ACA401/ACA-401D Course pack (Period 1) (EUCLID, 2024) and the additional assigned videos on Grammarly, a Basic ACA-401 Tutorial by Prof Cleenewerck, and Dr Gulma's Sample R.P. Review video. I find these materials very useful because, even though I have been through several years of studies, I have never really used many of the now-required functions of Microsoft Word, nor have I understood Style. I hope I have done justice to the materials given in this paper. Also, even though now I feel that the specifics of reviewing a paper are still elusive, I am confident that with time, I will master that, too.

I have selected the following five concepts from the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack for Period 1: starting, researching an essay, and organizing thoughts; punctuation; American versus British English; plagiarism and style guide; and Latin abbreviations.

2) STARTING, RESEARCHING AN ESSAY, AND ORGANISING THOUGHTS

I have always found these first steps the most difficult. Starting an essay is not only sitting down and putting thoughts on paper but a much more diverse and complex process. First, even deciding on the exact topic can take time, as many times, one has several thoughts or ideas flying about in one's head, and deciding on the best one can be difficult. I need to ask myself if the chosen topic is relevant to the task, how much I know about it, and if enough research material is available to delve into the topic deeper and present a multifaceted argument (EUCLID 2024, 8). To have enough time to make a settled, well-founded plan, one needs to have time, so one must start early with the essay (EUCLID 2024, 7). I agree with this sentiment; I always give myself enough time to write. Otherwise, I would be too anxious and stressed. As opposed to the suggested drafting of an initial plan (EUCLID 2024, 7), I always find it difficult and abandon it early on, not only because that plan changes a lot as I go along but also because I seem to gather knowledge as I do the research, and many times change the original essay topic, depending on what material I find. Of course, at the beginning, I had a vague idea of how I would structure the essay, but I have never followed it, so I did not take it as a strict guide. This relates to the suggestion given in the course pack (EUCLID 2024, 9) about keeping the research question clearly in mind throughout the writing process. Because I know that I may change the topic, I usually keep a somewhat flexible mind and consider other questions throughout. This might reflect bad planning, but you never know; my attitude to essay writing may change due to these Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) studies.

3) PUNCTUATION

Punctuation, for me, is important for several reasons. It not only gives clarity but also helps with emphasis and rhythm within a sentence. By using the correct punctuation, one knows when to pause, stop or even how to intonate. As we learned in this course, the use of apostrophes can be a mind field. For example, when indicating possession, they are not to be used in every case, such as Earls Court or All Souls College (EUCLID 2024, 16). I also found it surprising that one should refrain from using apostrophes after abbreviations and dates, such as MP's or 1970 (EUCLID 2024, 17). Based on this, I have been using it incorrectly. The use of semicolons is also very interesting. In my native tongue, Hungarian, we hardly use it. However, the same principles apply to English, such that it should only be used between logically connected or related sentence parts or when improved clarity is needed (EUCLID 2024, 18). However, on this latter occasion, I find it hard to identify. For example, the sample sentence is given: 'I visited the Ashmolean Museum, Oxford; the Victoria and Albert Museum, London; and the Pencil Museum, Keswick' (EUCLID 2024, 18). For me, it should be punctuated with commas: I visited the Ashmolean Museum in

Oxford, the Victoria and Albert Museum in London, and the Pencil Museum in Keswick. This way, to me, it is easier to read and understand. Using commas, though, shows an interesting difference between English and Hungarian rules. The example sentence ‘She left her money to her parents, Mother Theresa, and the pope’ would have been correct in Hungarian, but it seems there is an extra comma after ‘Theresa’ in the English version (EUCLID 2024, 20). I would also argue about the lack of a hyphen in ‘email’ instead of ‘e-mail’. Both are correct and widely used; as such, they should be accepted (EUCLID 2024, 21). I also identified a printing mistake within the course pack. In the section about quotation marks, the sample sentence “‘The kitchen’, he said, ‘is the heart of the home.’” is repeated twice, with one of the sentences being ticked, but the other labelled as incorrect (EUCLID 2024, 23) though written the same way.

4) AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

I find this chapter fascinating. I have lived for almost twenty years in the U.K., so by default, I use (or try to use) British English. American English, from afar, seems unregulated and chaotic to me, especially the way words are pronounced. I understand the reasons behind the dominance of its use (EUCLID 2024, 25), but to me, it is not based on the well-established, long-term term, and deep history and culture. Just because the U.S. has a much bigger population or wealth, so more influence on modern culture, media, and technology, it does not mean that their use of English should be considered as the baseline. I also understand that languages should be flexible and serve the user, but to keep a specific language, i.e., English, rules should be attached to it and adhered to. For example, the word ‘licence’ is a noun in British English, but ‘license’ is in American English. How can it be the same as the verb form? Or the words ‘check’ or ‘defense’ (EUCLID 2024, 25)? Both noun and verb forms are written the same way in the U.S., and I am sure it leads to confusion. These examples point to oversimplification as opposed to simplification, the latter of which should be the aim of any modern language to make it usable. On the other hand, I find words with different or additional meanings rather amusing. For example, ‘The opening of our new play was a bomb!’ (EUCLID 2024, 26). British people would never say that as it would soon be a police matter. The use of ‘English muffin’ (EUCLID 2024, 26) instead of ‘crumpets’ is a strange one. I wonder what word American people use for muffins baked in the U.K. Also, if British people use ‘thousand million’ (which, by the way, I have never heard of being used) for describing a billion (EUCLID, 2024, 26), then what would they use for expressing a hundred billion? The ‘pants’ versus ‘underpants’ situation is hilarious (EUCLID 2024, 26); I am sure it has led to lots of misunderstandings, though I thought Americans used ‘slacks’ instead of the British ‘trousers’. Similarly, a scenario I previously experienced was when I asked for a ‘rubber’ instead of an ‘eraser’ in an American College; at first, I did not understand the strange looks I got, but later, I was corrected.

5) **PLAGIARISM AND STYLE GUIDE**

Plagiarism, by EUCLID definition, is ‘when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information’ (EUCLID 2024, 34). Before embarking on my master’s and now this PhD degree studies, I have never really thought about plagiarism. I guess it is because, apart from my end of bachelor’s degree thesis, I have never written an academic piece. I completely understand that rules about plagiarism are there to give credit to or protect the author's intellectual property, and it should be a punishable offense not to do so. Citation is a way to avoid it. As there are several ways to cite the source of information, it can be tricky to apply, especially the format of referencing at the end of an academic piece. During my master’s degree, we used the Harvard style, but it seems the Chicago style is preferred in this program (EUCLID 2024, 50). I am sure I will get the gist of it, but learning and applying how books, journals, reports, documents, etc., are cited differently is a difficult and meticulous task. Fortunately, there are format samples in the course pack (EUCLID 2024, 50-57), which will be of great use during my studies.

6) **LATIN ABBREVIATIONS**

Even though I only learned a little Latin at university, with declinations but no conjugations included in the curriculum, I have always wanted to know more. Latin is said to be a dead language, but it is used more commonly than we care to admit. It is the basis of many modern languages and is used daily. It is great to see all the most common abbreviations and expressions used in academic writing summarised in a table format (EUCLID 2024, 59-64). Most of them I am familiar with, but some, for example, 'stet', 'sine die', 'scilicet', 'non sequitur', and 'bis', I am not. I make sure I learn them. Also, I find it important to use abbreviations correctly, especially in a foreign language with which not everyone is familiar. There are some abbreviations in the table which have more than one meaning, for example, 'v.' It can mean 'versus', 'vide' or 'voce' (EUCLID 2024, 61). It is important to know about these variations and apply them according to the context of the text.

7) **CONCLUSION**

In conclusion, after reading the course pack (EUCLID 2024), it is a very good support material and guide to my future studies in this program. It is clear and precise, and good examples are given. The associated videos by Prof Cleenewerck and Dr Gulma home the studied material even more and show its practical uses.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

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